

AN OVERVIEW OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS AND APPROACHES

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Annotation: *This investigated paper dedicated to the history of English language teaching methods. The work structurally consists from Introduction, 2 chapters and conclusion. The main part of the research contains information about methods of foreign language teaching as an applied, not a pure, science, since it is the scientific study not of language or of definite languages, but of the ways and means which can be used in teaching in order to facilitate, accelerate and generally make effective the assimilation by the learners of foreign languages as used by the native speakers and as scientifically studied and systematized in linguistics. The results of the work could be find at the conclusion part of the work.*

Keywords: *foreign language, communicative method, language, method, communication, The Direct Method, The Audiolingual Method, Cognitive Code Learning*

It has been estimated that some 60 percent of today's world population is multilingual. From both a contemporary and a historical perspective, bilingualism or multilingualism is the norm rather than the exception. It is fair, then, to say that throughout history foreign language learning has always been an important practical concern. Whereas today English is the world's most widely studied foreign language, 500 years ago it was Latin, for it was the dominant language of education, commerce, religion, and government in the Western world. In the sixteenth century, however, French, Italian, and English gained in importance as a result of political changes in Europe, and Latin gradually became displaced as a language of spoken and written communication.

The definite start of history of teaching/learning second/foreign language in the world is not known, but one thing is clear that since early age people(s) of different neighbourhoods, tribes, nations and cultures have had to address each other for certain reasons using various means from body-language up to communication their language. Passing dozens of ages this demand hasn't lost its value as mastering other language than

native one has one of the most important functions, i.e. language of diplomacy.

Debate and developments around the methods of language teaching and learning have been ongoing since the time of Comenius in the 17th century, if not before. The complexity of contexts and the greater appreciation of the issues lead us to the conclusion that the panacea of a single, universal optimum method for teaching and learning modern languages does not exist, but rather the need for teachers to adopt an informed eclectic approach, incorporating elements from the range of methods available. Most language teaching today aims to achieve oral communication, although some questionnaire respondents place greater emphasis upon grammatical mastery and reading.

In attempting to define what 'method' is, we can consider Edward Anthony's tripartite distinction of **Approach, Method and Technique** [7].

This distinction was developed and recast by Richards and Rodgers [21] as **Approach, Design and Procedure** encompassed within the overall concept of **Method**, "an umbrella term for the specification and interrelation of theory and practice" [21: 16] where

- *Approach* refers to the beliefs and theories about language, language learning and teaching that underlie a method
- *Design* specifies how theories of language and learning are implemented in a syllabus model and teaching and learning activities and materials in the classroom
- *Procedure* concerns the techniques and practices employed in the classroom as consequences of particular approaches and designs.

[21:17]

There are many publications available discussing the various methods. We have drawn here, inter alia, upon Chapter Two of H. Douglas Brown's *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy* [2].

Brown draws a distinction between **methods** as “specific, identifiable clusters of theoretically compatible classroom techniques” [2:15], and **methodology** as “pedagogical practices in general...Whatever considerations are involved in ‘how to teach’ are methodological” (ibid.).

A glance through the past century or so of language teaching will give an interesting picture of how varied the interpretations have been of the best way to teach a foreign language. As disciplinary schools of thought – psychology, linguistics, and education, for example – have come and gone, so have language-teaching methods waxed and waned in popularity. Teaching methods, as “approaches in action,” are of course the practical application of theoretical findings and positions. In a field such as ours that is relatively young, it should come as no surprise to discover a wide variety of these applications over the last hundred years, some in total philosophical opposition to others.

Albert Marckwardt [15:5] saw these “changing winds and shifting sands” as a cyclical pattern in which a new method emerged about every quarter of a century. Each new method broke from the old but took with it some of the positive aspects of the previous practices [2: 17-18].

The Grammar-Translation Method

The Classical or Grammar-Translation method represents the tradition of language teaching adopted in western society and developed over centuries of teaching not only the classical languages such as Latin and Greek, but also foreign languages. The focus was on studying grammatical rules and morphology, study, doing written exercises, memorizing vocabulary, translating texts from and prose passages into the language. It remained popular in modern language pedagogy, even after the introduction of newer methods. In America, the Coleman Report in 1929 recommended an emphasis on the skill of reading in schools and colleges as it was felt at that time that there would be few opportunities to practise the spoken language. Internationally, the Grammar-Translation method is still practised today, not only in courses, including CRAMLAP respondents, teaching the older forms of languages (Latin, Greek, Old Irish etc.) where its validity can still be argued in light of expected learning outcomes, but

also, with less justification, in some institutions for modern language courses. Prator and Celce-Murcia [20:3] listed the major characteristics of Grammar-Translation:

- Classes are taught in the mother tongue, with little active use of the target language;
- Much vocabulary is taught in the form of lists of isolated words;
- Long, elaborate explanations of the intricacies of grammar are given;
- Grammar provides the rules for putting words together, and instruction often focuses on the form and inflection of words;
- Reading of difficult classical texts is begun early;
- Little attention is paid to the context of texts, which are treated as exercises in grammatical analysis;
- Often the only drills are exercises in translating disconnected sentences from the target language into the mother tongue;
- Little or no attention is given to pronunciation.

The Direct Method

While Henri Gouin's *The Art of Learning and Studying Foreign Languages*, published in 1880, can be seen as the precursor of modern language teaching methods with its 'naturalistic' approach, the credit for popularizing the Direct Method usually goes to Charles Berlitz, although he marketed it as the Berlitz Method.

The basic premise of the Direct Method was that one should attempt to learn a second language in much the same way as children learn their first language. The method emphasized oral interaction, spontaneous use of language, no translation between first and second languages, and little or no analysis of grammar rules.

Richards and Rodgers summarized the principles of the Direct method as follows [21: 12]

- Classroom instruction was conducted exclusively in the target language;
- Only everyday vocabulary and sentences were taught;
- Oral communication skills were built up in a carefully graded progression organized around questions-and-answer exchanges between teachers and students in small intensive classes;
- Grammar was taught inductively;
- New teaching points were taught through modelling and practice;

- Concrete vocabulary was taught through demonstration, objects, pictures; Abstract vocabulary was taught through association of ideas;
- Both speech and listening comprehension were taught;
- Correct pronunciation and grammar were emphasized.

The Audiolingual Method

The Audiolingual Method is derived from "The Army Method," so called because it was developed through a U.S. Army programme devised after World War II to produce speakers proficient in the languages of friend and foes. In this method, grounded in the habit formation model of behaviourist psychology and on a Structural Linguistics theory of language, the emphasis was on memorization through pattern drills and conversation practices rather than promoting communicative ability.

Characteristics of the Audio-lingual Method:

- New material is presented in dialogue form;
- There is dependence on mimicry, memorization of set phrases, and overlearning
 - Structures are sequenced by means of contrastive analysis taught one at a time;
 - Structural patterns are taught using repetitive drills;
 - There is little or no grammatical explanation. Grammar is taught by inductive analogy rather than by deductive explanation;
 - Vocabulary is strictly limited and learned in context;
 - There is much use of tapes, language labs, and visual aids;
 - Great importance is attached to pronunciation;
 - Very little use of the mother tongue by teachers is permitted;
 - Successful responses are immediately reinforced;
 - There is a great effort to get students to produce error-free utterances;
 - There is a tendency to manipulate language and disregard content [20].

Cognitive Code Learning

With the Chomskyan revolution in linguistics, attention of linguists and language teachers was drawn towards the 'deep structure' of language and a more cognitive psychology. Chomsky's theory of Transformational-generative Grammar focused attention again on the rule-governed nature of language and language acquisition rather than habit formation. This gave rise in the 1960s to **Cognitive Code Learning** where learners were encouraged to work out grammar rules deductively for themselves.

This method had limited success as the cognitive emphasis on rules and paradigms proved as unattractive as behaviourist rote drilling. There is also confusion for practitioners, with Nunan [19: 6] ascribing inductive reasoning to it, while Brown [2: 24] notes that proponents of a cognitive code learning methodology injected more deductive rule learning into language classes

Deductive Learning	Grammatical explanations or rules are presented and then applied through practice in exercises. The learner works from rules/ principles to examples.
Inductive Learning	Learners are presented with examples. They then discover or induce language rules and principles on their own.

Alternative or 'Designer' methods

The 1970s saw the emergence of some alternative, less-commonly used methods and approaches, such as **Suggestopedia; The Silent Way; Total Physical Response**. An overview table of these 'Designer' methods is provided by Nunan [17: 194-195] and Brown 2: chapter 2].

The Natural Approach

The Natural Approach, with echoes of the 'naturalistic' approach of the Direct Method, was developed by Krashen and Terrell [14]. It emphasised "Comprehensible Input", distinguishing between 'acquisition' – a natural subconscious process, and 'learning' – a conscious process. They argued that learning cannot lead to acquisition. The focus is on meaning, not form (structure, grammar).

Nunan's overview of the Natural Approach [17, 194-195], adapted here, outlines its characteristics:

Theory of language	Theory of Learning	Objectives	Syllabus
The essence of language is meaning. Vocabulary not grammar is the heart of language	There are 2 ways of L2 language development: <u>Acquisition</u> a natural subconscious process; <u>Learning</u> a conscious process.	Designed to give beginners/ intermediate learner communicative skills. Four broad areas; basic personal communicative	Based on a selection of communicative activities and topics derived from learner needs

	Learning cannot lead to acquisition	skills (oral/written); academic learning skills (oral/written)	
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Activity types	Learner roles	Teacher roles	Roles of materials
Activities allowing comprehensible input, about things in the here-and-now. Focus on meaning not form	Should not try and learn language in the usual sense, but should try and lose themselves in activities involving meaningful communication	The teacher is the primary source of comprehensible input. Must create positive low-anxiety climate. Must choose and orchestrate a rich mixture of classroom activities	Materials come from realia rather than textbooks. Primary aim is to promote comprehension and communication

Krashen

The Natural Approach was based upon Krashen's theories of second language acquisition, and his Five Hypotheses. As we shall see, Krashen's influence went beyond this particular method and as such merits closer attention.

Krashen's Five Hypotheses
The Acquisition/Learning Hypothesis: claims that there are two distinctive ways of developing second language competence: <i>acquisition</i> , that is by using language for "real communication" <i>learning</i> .. "knowing about" or "formal knowledge" of a language
The Natural Order hypothesis; 'e acquire the rules of language in a predictable order'
The Monitor Hypothesis: 'conscious learning ... can only be used as a Monitor or an editor'(Krashen & Terrell 1983) and cannot lead to fluency
The Input Hypothesis: 'humans acquire language in only one way - by understanding messages or by receiving "comprehensible input"'
The Affective Filter Hypothesis: 'a mental block, caused by affective factors ... that prevents input from reaching the language acquisition device' [13:100]

The contrasts between Acquisition and Learning can be tabulated as follows [4]:

Acquisition	Learning
Implicit, subconscious	Explicit, conscious
Informal situations	Formal situations
Uses grammatical 'feel'	Uses grammatical rules
Depends on attitude	Depends on aptitudes
Stable order of acquisition	Simplex to complex order of learning

The use of the term 'Natural Approach' rather than 'Method' highlights the development of a move away from 'method' which implies a particular set of features to be followed, almost as a panacea, to 'approach' which starts from some basic principles which are then developed in the design and development of practice in teaching and learning. It is now widely recognized that the diversity of contexts requires an informed, eclectic approach. To quote Nunan:

It has been realized that there never was and probably never will be a method for all, and the focus in recent years has been on the development of classroom tasks and activities which are consonant with what we know about second language acquisition, and which are also in keeping with the dynamics of the classroom itself [18: 228].

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